

Research Article

Evaluation of Certain Immunological Markers and Cortisol in Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder

Amer Radhi Abdul Hussein ¹*¹Jabir ibn Hayyan for Medical and pharmaceutical University, Faculty of medical Science, Alnajaf, Iraq.*Corresponding author: amer.radhi@jmu.edu.iq**Article Info****Keywords:** Autism spectrum disorder, Interleukins, Tumor necrosis factor, Cortisol.**Received:** 15.01.2026;**Accepted:** 19.02.2026;**Published:** 23.02.2026**Abstract**

Significant behavioural and communicative impairments are hallmarks of autism spectrum disorder, a complex and diverse neurodevelopmental condition that includes a range of limitations. Numerous physiological and molecular biomarkers have been connected to the aetiology of autism. The current study used ELISA techniques to investigate the correlation between cortisol and plasma levels of several immunological markers in Iraqi children with autism spectrum disorder. The levels of cortisol, tumour necrosis factor alpha, interleukin-6, and interleukin-8 in children with autism differed significantly from those in the control group, according to the results.

 © 2026 by the author's. The terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license apply to this open access article.**1. Introduction**

A complex and diverse neurodevelopmental disease, autism spectrum disorder (ASD) includes a range of difficulties marked by notable behavioural and communicative impairments. The Centres for Disease Control and Prevention estimate that one out of every 59 8-year-old children in the US has an ASD diagnosis, with a noticeably higher prevalence seen in boys [1]. The role of cytokines in ASD has attracted significant attention in recent years. These immune system proteins are crucial in regulating the intricate interactions between the immune system and the central nervous system. Emerging evidence suggests that cytokines contribute to various neural processes, such as neurotransmitter function, neuroplasticity, and neuroendocrine activities [2].

Further studies reveal that the immune system influences both behavioral and cognitive functions, where there is a possible link between immune dysregulation and psychiatric symptoms [3–6]. Increasing evidence supports the concept that neuroinflammation is associated with impaired synaptic function and connectivity which is observed in numerous psychiatric disorders [7].

In ASD specifically, interleukin 6 (IL-6) has received attention for its dual function as both a pro-inflammatory and regenerative cytokine, resulting in complex impacts on metabolic and neuronal processes. Immunocytochemical studies have shown activation of microglia and astroglia cells in neuronal [8] and behavioral [9] disorders, along with heightened production of cytokines such as macrophage chemoattractant protein-1 (MCP-1) and transforming growth factor-beta 1 (TGF- β 1) within neuroglial cells [10]. As a member of the CXC chemokines subfamily [11], interleukin 8 (IL-8) is produced by several issues including blood cells [12]. The main target of the action of IL-8 is neutrophil, an action that activates neutrophil resulting in regulation of pathophysiological processes. One of the most pluripotent cytokines known is tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), which is consistently pro-inflammatory and produced systemically,

including by brain astrocytes and microglia. It is thought to play a significant role in inflammatory and autoimmune brain pathologies [13, 14]. Additionally, TNF- α is thought to be a factor in a number of neurodegenerative illnesses [15]. In the pathophysiology of several illnesses, including rheumatoid arthritis, inflammatory bowel disease, septic shock, and various autoimmune disorders, it works in concert with TNF- α [16]. These are the main pro-inflammatory cytokines that macrophages produce, and they have the ability to initiate a series of inflammatory responses [17, 18]. In a previous study, we measured the level of some heavy metals in children with autism [19]. In this study, we evaluated the level of IL-6, IL-8, TNF- α , and cortisol in children with autism.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Case and Control group

This research involved 84 children, 42 of whom were normal and 42 of whom had autism. With the consent of the local department of health, skilled laboratory professionals took fasting (8 am-9am) venous blood samples (about 3 ml each) from both groups. Samples were then stored in EDTA-containing tubes so that cortisol and cytokines could be measured.

2.2. Place and time of study

Numerous medical facilities and educational facilities in several Iraqi cities, including Najaf, Babylon, Karbala, Baghdad, Diwaniya, and Muthanna, participated in the study. It took place between October 2020 and December 2022.

2.3. Consent and ethical approval

A written consent was obtained from parents and an ethical approval was obtained from Jabir ibn Hayyan for Medical and pharmaceutical University / Faculty of medical Science.

2.4. Statistical analysis

GraphPad Prism 9.3.1/USA was used to show and analyze the data. Each graphic displays the the number of participants and compares children with autism to those without autism. The t-test was used to assess the degree of significance, and differences with a p-value of less than 0.05 were considered statistically different.

3. Results

3.1. Characterization of participants according to the age

Of the forty-two normal children, eighteen (42%) were between the ages of two and five, while the other twenty-four (58%) were older (six to ten years). Of the forty-two autistic children, sixteen (38%) were between the ages of two and five, while the other twenty-six (62%) were between the ages of six and ten Figure 1.

Figure 1: Characterization of participants according to the age.

3.2. Characterization of participants according to the gender.

Of the 42 normal participants, 19 (45%) were female and 23 (55%) were male. As seen in Figure 2, however, of the 42 autistic children, 30 (71%) were male and the remaining 12 (29%) were female.

Figure 2: Characterization of participants according to the gender

3.3. The blood levels of IL-6 in control and autistic children

In this study, we found significant higher levels of IL-6 and IL-8 in children with autism ($P < 0.05$). The serum concentration of IL-6 in control was $2.58 \pm 0.3 \mu\text{g/ml}$ while its concentration in serum from autistic children reached $7.2 \pm 0.55 \mu\text{g/ml}$ as shown in Figure 3

Figure 3: Serum concentration of IL-6 in healthy and autistic children (mean \pm SEM, $n=42$, * $p > 0.001$ compared to control, t-test).

3.4. The blood levels of IL-8 in control and autistic children

The concentration of IL-8 in children with autistic was $10.11 \pm 0.65 \mu\text{g/ml}$ which was significantly higher compared to its level in control ($5.99 \pm 0.34 \mu\text{g/ml}$) as shown in Figure 4.

3.5. The blood levels of TNF- α in control and autistic children

For TNF- α plasma levels, our data revealed a significantly higher level in the autistic group (8.77 ± 2.08) compared to its level in healthy group ($4.91 \pm 0.65 \mu\text{g/ml}$) as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4: Serum concentration of IL-8 in healthy and autistic children (mean \pm SEM, n=40, * $p < 0.001$ compared to control, t-test).

Figure 5: Serum concentration of TNF- α in healthy and autistic children (mean \pm SEM, n=40, * $p > 0.05$ compared to control, t-test).

3.6. The blood levels of cortisol in control and autistic children

It was found the serum concentration of cortisol is significantly higher ($P < 0.001$) in children with autistic spectrum disorder compared to that in healthy control groups (27.34 ± 4.81 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 8.79 ± 2.50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, respectively) as shown in Figure 6.

4. Discussion

The presents study evaluated the levels of cytokine (IL-6, IL-8 and TNF- α) and cortisol in the blood samples of healthy children and those with autistic spectrum disorder. Our findings revealed significantly high levels of IL-6, IL-8, TNF- α and cortisol in children with autistic spectrum disorder compared to healthy children. An increasing number of researches highlighted the potential role for dysregulated immunological responses in autism. Numerous theories, including childhood immunizations, heightened frequency of family autoimmunity, and maternal immunological abnormalities during early pregnancy, have sought to connect autism with defective immune activity. Inflammatory cytokine expression has recently been found to be elevated in the peripheral blood, brain, and cerebrospinal fluid of autistic individuals in a number of study lines [20–23]. Specifically, it has been repeatedly observed that the autistic brain has elevated IL-6 [24–26]. Another important mechanistic pathway in maternal immune activation that has been proposed to be connected to autism is IL-6 signaling [27]. Astrocytes, microglia, and neurons are among the cellular sources of IL-6 in the central nervous system [28, 29]. More details about the role of microglia and astrocytes can be seen the review article [8]. The level of IL-6 expression has been shown to be elevated in pathological conditions [30]. It is uncertain, nonetheless, if the elevated IL-6 expression in the autistic brain has particular behavioral role. Consistent with signs and symptoms of autism, those mice with high levels of IL-6 in the brain showed reduced social interaction, aberrant anxiety-like traits and habituation, learning deficiencies, and diminished cognitive abilities.

Figure 6: Serum concentration of cortisol in healthy and autistic children (mean \pm SEM, n=40, * p>0.001 compared to control, t-test).

Evidence suggests that specific cytokines can affect behavior and neurodevelopment [31, 32] and that inflammation and microglia activation have a role in the pathophysiology of neuropsychiatric disorders, including ASDs [2, 33]. Neuronal activity, survival, and proliferation may all be directly changed by IL-6, which may have an effect on behavior [34]. Additionally, IL-6 affects memory and learning in physiological and pathological ways [35]. Postmortem specimens of the temporal cortex of the brain of people with ASDs [36] showed elevated IL-6 gene expression, while the brain and cerebrospinal fluid of people with ASDs showed increased IL-6 protein levels [25]. These results are supported by the fact that ASD patients' frontal brain and cerebellum have considerably higher levels of IL-6 than age-matched controls.

One chemokine type that contributes to autoimmune diseases is IL-8 [37], which mainly causes chemotaxis and phagocytosis [38]. IL-8 may also have a role in neurodevelopment [39, 40] or in regulating neuronal electrical activity [41]. Children with ASD exhibited much higher plasma levels of IL-8 than healthy controls, according to a 2015 meta-analysis by Masi and colleagues [42].

In the current investigation, we also found that children with ASDs had considerably higher blood TNF- α levels than healthy controls. Another study found that after being stimulated with polyhydroxy alkanoates and tetanus, autistic participants' peripheral blood mononuclear cells produced more TNF [34]. The CSF fluid of children with ASD had about 50 times higher levels of TNF [21]. TNF can be secreted by brain mast cells [43]. The brains of children with ASDs [25] have been shown to exhibit both TNF and IL-6, and IL-6 has been linked to an animal "model" of autism [44]. Mast cells [45, 46] secrete preformed TNF, which promotes T-cell activation. In the hippocampus, TNF has been connected to neurite development and the control of homeostatic synaptic plasticity [47].

We found that the ASD diagnosis was associated with changes in the plasma concentrations of several cytokines in the children with ASD. Even while several of the cytokines that were significantly changed in our current study have been documented in earlier research [34, 48, 49], some of the findings were inconsistent [50, 51], contradictory, or both [52, 53]. Inconsistencies may have resulted from methodological problems as well as the various clinical characteristics of the participants in these investigations. Moreover, the designs of a large number of earlier clinical investigations were unable to provide light on the reasons behind the aberrant cytokine levels in ASD. In conclusion, we found that the levels of IL-6, IL-8, TNF- α and cortisol were higher in children with autism compared to their level in healthy children. Further studies are required to investigate the level of other cytokines especially anti-inflammatory cytokines in children with autism. In addition, the correlation between the severity of autism and the level of cytokines.

Article Information

Disclaimer (Artificial Intelligence): The author(s) hereby declare that NO generative AI technologies such as Large Language Models (ChatGPT, COPILOT, etc.), and text-to-image generators have been used during writing or editing of manuscripts.

Competing Interests: Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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